

Supervisory Skills of Principals and Teachers' Job Performance in Delta State

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DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.13825390](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13825390)

Abstract

This study was carried out to ascertain supervisory skills of principals' and teachers' job performance in Delta-State. The population consists of (10,856) teachers and (439) principals in public secondary schools. The population covered only public secondary schools in Delta State in the 3 Senatorial Districts. A simple random sampling technique was used to obtain a sample of 390 respondents which comprised teachers (350) and principals (40) respectively in public secondary schools of Delta State. The research instrument used for this study is the Questionnaire. The instrument was self-designed by the researcher and titled "Principals Supervisory Skills and Teachers' Job Performance (PSSTJPQ). To ensure the reliability of the research instrument, the test-retest method was adopted. Findings showed that Principals' had strong communication skills and communicated effectively about things happening in the school to teachers, principals possessed human relation skills used to motivate, interact and inspire teachers in the supervisory process. Teachers' commitment to job task, regular attendance to school, teachers' practical knowledge of subject matter, ability to teach effectively, early submission of up-to-date lesson notes and other records, as well as teachers' display of creativity and discipline are important criteria for assessing teachers' job performance. It is recommended that principals should be made to understand the significance of supervision in the school and be sensitized to improve their commitment level to supervisory practices.

Keywords: Principals, supervisory skills, teachers, job performance.

Introduction

The significance of education as a tool for a nation's socioeconomic and political growth was underlined in the Federal Government of Nigeria's new National Policy on Education, which referred to education as an instrument for national development. Any nation's progress requires competent workforce, which education provides. It's vital to remember that education is more than just schooling; schooling at all levels helps to reach the high goals of education. Effective teaching and learning is one of the most critical components in achieving these goals. As a result, the importance of good supervision cannot be overstated, since supervision's main goal is "effectiveness of teaching and learning."

The phrase "supervision" is derived from two basic words: "super" and "vision," both of which imply "to watch over." In general, supervision is a method of advising, guiding, refreshing, encouraging, stimulating, improving, and supervising certain groups with the hope of persuading people to stop using incorrect procedures in performing certain functions on their jobs while also emphasizing the importance of good human relations in an organisation (Akalaia, 2011). Supervision is the act of leading, supporting, motivating, and supervising instructors in order to make them productive and efficient in the teaching and learning process, according to Ifedilli (2016). According to Osakwe (2010), it is also concerned with providing professional aid and direction to teachers in order to accomplish successful teaching and learning in the school. Thus, educational supervision is the process or act of ensuring that the policies, concepts, and techniques designed for accomplishing educational goals are followed correctly and effectively. This approach entails employing expert knowledge and experience to supervise, assess, and collaboratively improve the circumstances and ways of doing things that are related to teaching and learning in schools that are related to teaching and learning. That is why, according to Bernard and Goodyear (2008), The involvement of a senior member of a profession to a younger member or members of the same profession is known as supervision.

The importance of overseeing the educational process cannot be overstated, since most school activities and all school programmes need monitoring. The practice of aiding instructors in improving their own schools and their instructional skills in order to increase successful teaching and learning is known as supervision of instruction (Afianmagbon, 2007), "Better instructors make for a better educational system," as the saying goes. As a result, it is a service provided to teachers with the goal of ensuring the quality of their classroom education. The goal of instructional supervision is to identify areas of work that need to be improved. Instructional supervision is critical for a variety of reasons which includes, "To evaluate and know the performance of teachers who have been hired to teach, to give specialized aid to teachers with day-to-day challenges, and to create possibilities for teachers' growth, all with the purpose of achieving educational goals. The supervisors' major role is to ensure that high standards are maintained and that the schools are conducted in line with the rules. As a supervisor, the principal gives professional supervision to teachers in order to strengthen their competences for a successful teaching process that benefits students' learning and progress.

All of the actions carried out by the teacher in order to accomplish the intended impacts on students are included in the teachers' job performance. It refers to how much a teacher engages in the general operation of the school in order to meet the school's anticipated objectives and goals. In other words, teachers' performance is critical to meeting school objectives. Presently, because of the inadequacy of skills for supervision, teachers still show a non-challant attitude to work, Also, most teachers were employed based on people they know in the industry and if they are not properly supervised they would not be effective in teaching. Students' performance in external examinations such as West Africa School Certificate (WASC) can be used as a more recent tool for analyzing teachers' job performance. In the last five years, according to Holland (2012) the

performance of students has been in the orbit of 31% to 39%. In 2012, it was 38.81%, 2013 it was 36.57%, 2014 was 31.28%, and in 2015 it was 38.68%. Though, in 2016 there was a considerable increase to 53% which broke the jinx of mass failure, it is not regarded as an excellent performance yet and measures still need to be put in place for it to be sustainable. However, it is important to highlight that the perceived ineffectiveness of secondary school teachers in performing their tasks may be linked to a variety of issues. This research, is however limited to principals' supervising abilities as a significant determinant in teachers' job efficacy. If instructors are not properly monitored, their efficacy in the classroom may suffer, and the educational goals may not be met. This may also result in poor instructional quality and, inevitably, a lack of dedication on the part of instructors, resulting in school inefficiency.

Concept of Supervision

The word supervision does not have a universal meaning; nonetheless, authorities have defined it in a variety of ways to fit their individual needs, and it revolves around a common subject. According to the British Journal of Hospital Medicine (2009), if vision implies "seeing," supervision may be understood as "over-seeing," or looking over someone's shoulder to check on them, as well as "super" in the sense of assisting someone to expand their professional abilities and knowledge. The job of supervision, then, is to modify the behaviours of people and organizations in order to guarantee that their performance is in line with plans. Plans must be developed, but they are unlikely to be realized unless activities are tracked and deviations from plans are detected and remedied as soon as possible.

As a result, supervision aids in providing the proper direction to the supervisee, allowing them to take initiative and assume responsibility for moving forward on their own. Mills (1997) argument that supervision has a direct impact on employee performance was highlighted by Osa (2012).

The need for supervisory skills in teachers' supervision

Principals are critical to the success of their schools' administration. In Nigeria, secondary school principals are chosen from among serving teachers based on the number of years they have served in the classroom, with the majority of them having no previous training or experience in educational administration or supervisory management. Principals in Nigeria's public secondary schools have been criticized on multiple occasions for their impact on student achievement, which indicates teacher's job performance. These complaints highlight the critical role that principals play in schools, as well as the high expectations that the public has for them. According to Mills (2007), supervision has a direct impact on instructors' work effectiveness. Supervisors allocate tasks with defined responsibilities for completion, and they demand accuracy and punctuality from assignees in return.

According to research, supervisors should have certain working knowledge and abilities in order to give instructors the essential help, advice, and support services for better classroom (Glickman et al, 2004; Holland, 2012). The lack of supervisory training has a negative impact on school management. To complete the numerous supervisory responsibilities to which they are called, a

supervisor must have a diverse set of knowledge, skills, and methodologies (Oliva & Pawlas, 2004).

As a result, Lunenburg (2010) believes that supervisors must learn three essential skills: conceptual skills, technical skills, and human connection skills, in order to deliver successful supervisory service.

Concept of Teachers Job Performance

Several studies suggest that the word "job performance" is widely used, but that it is still a poorly defined notion. It is, however, the field of psychology that deals with the workplace, and it is most usually used to relate to whether or not a person does a good job. Performance is a critical measure for determining organizational results and success. The core of every educational system is its teachers. They remain the most important predictor of educational quality at all levels of the educational system. 'No educational system can rise beyond the caliber of its instructors,' says the updated National Policy on Education (2004). The teacher, according to the National Curriculum Conference of 1969, is the "essential man in the overall educational programme." This, on the other hand, is to demonstrate that teacher effectiveness is critical to achieving specified educational objectives. Campbell (2007) defined performance as a variable at the individual level. This means that performance is something that is done by a single individual. He went on to say that performance is defined as an employee's behaviour. The terms "performance" and "outcomes" are not interchangeable. Outcomes are the consequence of an individual's efforts, but they are also influenced by other factors. Performance, according to Campbell, does not have to be plainly visible individual behaviours. It may be made up of mental outputs like replies or decisions. Whether the performance of interest is mental or behavioural, it must be within the control of the person. Organizational objectives that are related to the job performance standard must be the focus of performance. Teachers' capacity to perform is derailed through little or no in-service training programmes (this is a key role of supervisors, to provide in-service training programmes to teachers) for teachers to widen their knowledge to avoid incompetency.

Criteria for Measuring Teachers' Job Performance

It is correctly said that 'where performance is measured performance improves'. However, one of the core questions in education is how to properly measure teacher performance. In other words, how to properly evaluate how good the teacher is still lacks a general consensus. Most people at work like to know how well they are doing in their jobs, Some may camouflage this desire but the vast majority of people at work want to do a good job and be known for doing a good job. Above all, they want their good job to be recognized by those who are in position to know that good job is being performed.

Assessing the quality of a staff is very difficult in school management but the guiding principle is that an individual should be effective in their duties. In the first place, a teacher needs to have the ideas of what he teaches, how he teaches and the ideas needs to be clearly formulated and communicated either verbally or in paper. The next element in qualitative assessment of staff

performance may be the ability to overcome obstacles be they financial, interpersonal or technical in translating ideas to practice. The basis for measuring the performance of a teacher is not easy to identify and define, some elements which enter into assessment are punctuality and absence, students' examination achievement under National curriculum or external examination system and individual financial management under school budget.

Doherty (2009) listed similar aspects of teaching performance under personality variables, teaching variables and achievement variables. But a more comprehensive and more detailed criteria for judging teaching performance offered by Edem (2008) is presented below:

- ❖ Teachers' personal traits: (a) Personal qualities to teach, enthusiasm and liveliness about teaching; (b) School relations: working well with others and the head of one's department.
- ❖ Teachers' performance on the job: (a) Lesson planning (b) Delivery and development of idea (c) Effective teacher-pupil relationship (d) Communication skill 3) Mastery of subject4) Attainment of aims.

Research Problem

If the goal of supervision is to enhance teachers' job performance thereby enhancing teaching and learning, there seems to be incidences of students' failure in examinations which seem to be fast re-occurring in public schools and indicates lapses in the area of supervision. Many administrators seem to be uncommitted to supervision, there is a lack of effective monitoring and assessment of students' learning outcomes, and there are insufficient training facilities to improve teachers for professional development and greater productivity. It's also been said that teachers don't get enough feedback, which impacts the working relationship between administrators and instructors. Recently, the Federal Government of Nigeria announced that Principals of all unity schools (government secondary schools) must sit up in their supervisory roles to ensure student excellent performance in external examinations or else they would be placed on permanent leaves from their jobs.

These remarks suggest that principals have significant obstacles, in part due to gaps and shortcomings in their supervisory responsibilities. As a result, an analytical assessment of the impact of principals' supervision abilities on teacher job performance is required, and this is the study's issue.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of this study is to assess supervisory skills of principals and teachers' job performance in Delta State. Specifically, the study aims at determining:

1. Principals' supervisory skills in public secondary schools in Delta state.
2. The criteria for evaluating teachers' job performance in Delta State.
3. The relationship between Principals' supervisory commitment and teachers' job performance?

Research Questions

Based on the above, the following research questions are raised;

1. What are the principals' supervisory skills in public secondary schools in Delta state?
2. What are the criteria for assessing teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Delta State?
3. What is the relationship between Principals' supervisory commitment and teachers' job performance?

Research hypotheses

H₀₁- here is no significant relationship between principals' supervisory commitment and teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Delta-Sate.

H₀₂- There is no relationship between principals' supervisory approach and teachers' job performance.

Method

The study was conducted using a descriptive survey research approach. This approach was chosen because it lets researchers to study a group of people or an object by gathering and analysing data from a small number of individuals or things that are deemed typical of the total population. As a result, it serves the twin purposes of analysing a huge population of secondary schools in Delta state as well as identifying and examining individual population characteristics. In Delta-State, there are 439 secondary schools, as well as (10,856) teachers and principals. Only public secondary schools in Delta State's 3 Senatorial Districts were covered by the population. The sample size was calculated using Nwana's guidelines in Nwagu (2013), which said that sample sizes for certain populations should be at least 40% for a population of a few hundreds, 20% for many hundreds, 10% for few thousands, and not more than 5% for several thousands. The researcher created a questionnaire named "Principals Supervisory Skills and Teachers' Job Performance Questionnaire that was used to collect data for the study (PSSTJPQ). The items were created with the goal of eliciting the respondents' thoughts on the subject of the study. The mean and standard deviation of the gathered data were used to examine the data. At a significance level of 0.05, the hypotheses were evaluated using Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC).

Result

Research question one

What are the principals' supervisory skills in public secondary schools in Delta state?

Table 1: Responses on Principals’ supervisory skills in public secondary schools,

S/N	ITEMS on Principals' Supervisory Skills	SA	A	D	SD
1.	Conceptual Skill Principals use professional knowledge , methods and techniques to support teachers' instructional activities	200	74	48	28
	Principals think through ideas as well as accept teachers' opinions to make effective decisions to accomplish school goals	140	185	12	13
3	Technical Skill Principal' works with teachers' to identify and solve common classroom problems for better job performance	132	129	40	49
4.	Communication Skill Principals' communicates to teachers on activities taking place in the school	150	100	85	15
5.	Human Relation Skill Principal' interacts, relates, motivates, inspires, and guides teachers towards better job performance	35	220	60	35
6	Evaluation Skill Principals evaluates teachers performance based on certain standards.	20	8	155	167

Table 1.1: Frequencies and Percentage of Research question 1

Skills	Agree		Disagree	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
Technical Skill	261	75%	89	25 %
Human Relation Skill	255	73%	95	27%
Communication Skill	250	71%	100	29%
Conceptual Skill	274	78%	68	22%
Evaluation Skill	28	18%	322	82%

Table 1.2: Mean and Standard deviation Ratings of Research Question 1

Skills	Mean	Standard Deviation	Decision
Technical Skill	2.9	.62	Agree
Human Relation Skill	2.7	.60	Agree
Communication Skill	3.1	.50	Agree
Conceptual Skill	3.2	.50	Agree
Evaluation Skill	1.66	.96	Disagree

Criterion mean- 2.50

Items 1, 2, 3, and 4 have high mean ratings, according to the data in the table above. Item 1 had a mean score of and a standard deviation of .62. Question number two has a mean score of 2.7 and a standard deviation of .60, while question number three has a mean score of 3.1 and a standard deviation of .50. The mean score for item question 4 is 3.2, with a standard deviation of .50. The mean score for item question 5 was 1.66, with a standard deviation of .96.

Research question two

What are the criteria for assessing teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Delta State?

Table 2: Responses on criteria for assessing teachers' job performance in public secondary schools.

S/N	Criteria for Assessing Teachers' Job Performance	SA	A	D	SD
1	Teachers' Commitment to regular attendance is a good criteria to judge teachers' job performance	178	172	-	-
2	Students performance is the major criteria used to judge teachers performance	110	58	22	160
3	Teachers practical knowledge of the subject matter and ability to teach effectively is an indicator of a teacher who performs well	182	168	-	-
4	Early Submission of up to date lesson notes and other records shows a teachers performance at his job	174	156	18	2
5	Teachers display of creativity and discipline is an important criteria for evaluating job performance	157	185	8	-

Table 2.1: Frequency and Percentage on Research Question 2

Criteria's	Agree		Disagree	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
Teachers commitment to job task and regular school attendance	390	100%	-	-

Student Performance	188	48.2%	202	51.8%
Teachers practical knowledge of subject matter and teach effectively	390	100%	-	-
Early submission of up to date records such as lesson notes, plans, register etc	370	95%	20	5%
Teachers' creativity and discipline	378	97%	12	3%

The table above reveals teachers’ responses to criteria used in assessing their performance, 390(100%) agreed that teachers commitment to job task and regular school attendance, teachers practical knowledge of subject matter and ability to teach is a useful criteria used in assessing them .370(95%) agreed and 20(5%) disagreed to early submission of up to date school records, 378(97%) agreed and 12(3%) disagreed to teachers creativity and discipline. However, 188(48.2%) agreed and 202(51.8%) disagreed to skills student performance being used as a criteria to judge teachers' performance.

Table 2.2: Mean and Standard Deviation ratings on Research Question 2

Questionnaire Item	Mean	Standard Deviation	Decision
Teachers commitment to job task and regular school attendance	3.52	.56	Agree
Student Performance	2.37	.82	Disagree
Teachers practical knowledge of subject matter and ability to teach effectively	3.51	.56	Agree
Early submission of up to date records such as lesson notes, plans, reiterated	3.67	.58	Agree
Teachers' creativity and discipline	3.48	49	Agree

Criterion mean- 2.50

The table above indicates that all the items on the questionnaire in response to research question 2 has a high mean score except item question 2 with a low mean score of 2.37 reflecting that respondents disagreed to student performance being a major criteria for assessing teachers job performance in Delta-state.

Research question 3 would be hypothesized alongside hypotheses 1 and 2.

Analysis of Research Hypotheses

Research Question 3 and Research hypothesis 1

There is no significant relationship between principals' supervisory commitment and teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Delta-Sate.

Table 3: Pearson Correlation Result on the Relationship between Principals' Supervisory Commitment and Teachers Job Performance

Variables	N	X	SD		r-cal	r-crit	Level of Significance	Decision
Principals Supervisory Skills	390	15.26	3.45					
Teachers Job Performance	390	76.41	10.71	388	0.468	0.195	0.05	Rejected

At the 0.05 level of significance, the result demonstrates that r-calculated (0.468) is larger than r-critical (0.195). As a result, the null hypothesis was disproved. The alternative hypothesis was accepted, implying that there is a link between the supervisory commitment of principals and teacher job effectiveness. The table below illustrates this

Research hypothesis 2

There is no relationship between principals' supervisory approach and teachers' job Performance.

Table 4: Pearson Correlation Result on the Relationship between Principals' Supervisory Approach and Teachers Job Performance

Variables	N	X	SD		r-cal	r-crit	Level of Significant	Decision
Principal Supervisory Approach	390	12.26	1.89					Rejected
Teachers' Job Performance	390	78.90	10.15	388	0.548	0.195	0.05	

The table above reveals that r-cal (0.548) is greater than r-crit (0.195) at 0.05 significant level, the statistical decision therefore was rejection of hypothesis which stated that the supervisory

approach of principals would not affect teachers' job performance. Thus, it is accepted that the supervisory approach of principals would affect teachers' job performance.

Discussion of Findings

Result from the analysis of the research question shows that the respondents were of the opinion that Principals' had strong communication skills and communicated effectively about things happening in the school to teachers, principals possessed human relation skills used to motivate, interact, inspire teachers in the supervisory process. It also showed that the respondents were of the opinion that principals' lacked evaluation skills that helps tell them their areas of strengths and weaknesses for further improvement. This therefore shows that Principals in Delta state have more technical skill, human relation skill, communication skill, and conceptual skill, but lack evaluation skill.

This finding is in line with the findings of Osaе (2012) that Principals possess communication skills, human relation skills. etc. But this study further discovered Principals lacks evaluation skill and thus need to develop evaluation skills as this is very crucial to the accomplishment of school goals. As rightly noted by Northhouse (2010), Principals must establish standards to judge performance and provide feedback to teachers. Feedback is very important as it helps the evaluation results to be communicated and affected for greater effectiveness, Result from Research Question 2 showed that teachers' commitment to job task, regular attendance to school, teachers practical knowledge of subject matter, ability to teach effectively, early submission of up to date lesson notes and other records, as well as teachers display of creativity and discipline are important criteria's for assessing teachers' job performance. The result further showed that student's performance as a major criteria used in assessing teachers' job performance is largely disagreed to. Some teachers noted while filling the questionnaire that student performance cannot be used because some students are very unserious and possess a laissez faire attitude to school work and thus cannot perform well to reflect the teachers' effort at his own job. This is in line with Smith (2012) findings in the literature which reviewed that student test scores as a popular criteria used in assessing teachers; job performance has been faced with many controversies and it is not an effective tool for judging teachers' performance.

Result from Research Question 3 and Hypothesis 1 showed that there is a significant relationship between Principals Supervisory Commitment and Teachers' Job Performance. This finding further

corresponds with the finding of Kipng'etich and Amed (2012) from their study on headteachers' perception of the roles in secondary schools in Kenya, where head teachers or principals affirmed that their commitment to supervisory roles or activities had great effect on teachers job performance. Respondents agreed that principals favour managerial activities than instructional supervisory activities, which further affirms the findings of Kipng'etich and Ahmed (2012) that Principals' were overloaded with managerial activities and had little or no time for instructional supervision. Furthermore, teachers disagreed to being motivated by principals to attend professional development programs. It was also revealed that principals' commitment to classroom

supervision was practically low. In all, respondents agreed that principals' supervisory commitment helps teachers' job performance. Principals only ensure professional records are marked regularly but the other aspect such as visitation of classes, organizing seminars, giving access to professional development programmes are being neglected. Ifedilli (2013) noted that Principals must carry out supervision through classroom observation, conferences, staff meetings, interschool visitation, checking of professional records etc on a regular basis because it leads to school development and teachers' effectiveness.

Finally, hypothesis 4 showed that there is a significant relationship between principals' supervisory approach and teachers' job performance. In other words, supervisory approach affects teachers' job performance negatively or positively depending on the type of approach used, However, this study found out from the mean ratings on the principals' supervisory approach in public secondary schools Delta-State that principals approach is fairly democratic in nature.

Conclusion

The outcomes of this research clearly illustrates that the link between the inputs and the related outputs has a significant impact on the efficacy of instructors' work performance. Teachers' work performance is influenced by inputs into the school system, such as principals' supervision abilities in terms of conceptual, technical, human connection, and evaluation skills, among others. Other elements, such as the dedication of administrators to supervision, their method to supervision, and the availability of facilities, all have an influence on teachers' job performance and successful supervision.

The previous results lead to the conclusion that certain principals lack supervisory abilities, notably in the areas of assessment, supervision knowledge, dedication to regular supervisory activities, and supervision methodology. It is obvious that if administrators' supervisory conduct improves, teachers' work performance will increase. The study equally established that teachers' assessment should not be based on student academic performance alone so as to avoid the teachers focusing on teaching students for test rather than learning purposes.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were deemed suitable based on the results of this investigation.

1. Stakeholders (federal, state, and local governments) should place a higher premium on improving teacher job performance via sufficient training and in-service training.
2. Principals should be educated on the need of supervision in the classroom and should be sensitized to increase their commitment to supervisory techniques.
3. Principals should make every effort to ensure that the rules and regulations that govern their instructors' behaviour are fair and flexible.
4. Leadership development programmes for principals should be developed.
5. Information should be disseminated quickly, and administrators should be prepared to address the school's aims and ambitions with instructors.

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